

ROLE OF RECOVERY RELATED SELF EFFICACY ON EMPLOYEE LONGEVITY IN INDIAN IT SECTOR

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Abstract

The Indian IT area is the most honored area for the country as it has procured name and acclaim both inside limited ability to focus time. Representatives life span in this examination has taken two significant factors each from authoritative elements and individual variables, work fulfillment and balance between fun and serious activities. The target of this exploration was to recognize whether there is any connection between's recovery related self efficacy and employee longevity and to distinguish the effect of recovery related self efficacy on employee longevity. Information were gathered from different IT area employees(220) in India. The information were broke down utilizing SPSS 20 and convenient examining was utilized to gather the information. Then the information were examined utilizing Kaplan-Meier strategy. Results show that recovery related self efficacy is having positive relationship with 2 dimensions of employee longevity ,i.e. job satisfaction and work life balance and furthermore with Employee longevity as the critical p esteem is 0.000 for each of the three factors. Additionally the R2 esteem shows that Work life balance is 9.1% impacted by recovery related self efficacy and job satisfaction is 11.6%. Likewise it shows that recovery related self efficacy is influencing more on job satisfaction as opposed to on Work life balance.

Keywords: Recovery Related Self Efficacy, Employee Longevity, Job Satisfaction, Work-Life Balance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indian IT sector is the most blessed sector for the country as it has earned name and fame both within short span of time. As a factor of success , it has taken many elements into consideration and one of them is People Management. When employees are facilitated with many benefits and also with a stress free environment, they have proven their skills being multiplied over time.

One such competency that have developed is recovery related self efficacy where employees' self ability to re-energize himself for the next day to work is been considered (Sonnentag & Bayer, 2005). A lot of research has been done to improve the efficiency of organization from employees point of view and recovery related self efficacy is one such factor.

The need arised when employees suffered from physical and mental health issue because of the work stress(Chen, 2013). And then there occurred the imbalances between family and work life(Gragnano, A., Simbula, S., & Miglioretti, 2020).

Studies found that employee well being improves when they are off work and then it degrades when they are at work(Westman et al., 1997; Westman et al., 2001; Strauss-Blasche et al., 2000). So, this research has tried to identify if there is some implication of high recovery related self efficacy on employee's decision to stay longer in the organisation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recovery related self efficacy is meant by the employees' ability to get himself recovered from work stress. The methods of getting oneself recovered is many and some of them might be spending time with friends and family and some might also be giving oneself a Me-Time where one can have his own space to get himself relaxed or it might be vacation or a pleasant evening or a walk .(Sonnentag et al., 2010). The research alludes to a singular's assumption for having the option to get benefit from recovery time and recovery opportunity as recovery related self efficacy and expect that recovery related self efficacy is a significant indicator of mental separation from work during off-work time(Fritz et al., 2010). On the off chance that one expects that one can sufficiently recuperate during off-work time, one is bound to start exercises that assistance to segregate from work and to recuperate(Karabinski et al., 2021). Regardless of whether work related contemplations come into mind, one will see these considerations as transient that can be "survive" soon. Hence, one is more averse to harp on work related contemplations. In any case, on the off chance that one expects that one won't prevail with regards to recuperating during off-work time, one will be less inclined to start supportive exercises(Sonnentag & Bayer, 2005). A few explores has been finished on recovery related self efficacy across the globe and the low self adequacy individuals were viewed as having serious wellbeing illnesses causing cerebrum strokes , heart failure any some more (Park and lee,2015). Another study was done by (Hanh et al., 2011) to identify the impact of recovery related self efficacy on job stress when recovery training was been given and the findings showed that recovery was improved with the training also the stress and sleep quality was improved. So Recovery training was also considered a mandate for the organizations as they suggest ways how to recover with a limited time.

Employee Longevity:

Employee longevity is understood as employees decision to stay longer in an organization.It depends on multiple factors and strongly depends on the organizational factors and personal factors. Employees longevity in this research has taken two major variables each from organizational factors and personal factors, job satisfaction and work life balance. Researchers have proven that the main reason behind employees' decision to quit organization are toxic environment in the workplace, gender biasness, poor organization communication, job security, poor assistance of supervisor and their implications on mental and physical health (Tolliver,2018;Salminen,2019 ;Yamoah,2014;Osteraker,1999; Sheridan ,1992) . Based on these studies the objectives of the study are framed.

3. OBJECTIVE

- To identify the correlation between Recovery related self Efficacy and Employee Longevity.
- To identify the impact of Recovery related self efficacy on Employee Longevity.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire was floated to approx 300 responses and total of 220 responses were taken for consideration. SPSS 20 was used to Analyse the data and convenient sampling was used to collect the data from various IT sector employees in India.

Kodja’s 6-item scale were taken to measure Recovery related self Efficacy with 5 point Likert Scale. The sample questionnaire are “I feel confident to be able to recover during off-job time even when I am tired” & “I feel confident to be able to recover during off-job time even when I am angry about something”. For Employee Longevity, This study has observed 2 dimensions , Job satisfaction and Employee work life balance. For job satisfaction, Ather’s 11-item questionnaire was taken and for work life balance, Banu’s 5- item scale was used. Liker 5 point scale was used to measure the responses. Some of the sample questions from job satisfaction are “In my organization, there are many chances to get promotion in my career.” & “I am always satisfied with my Head for his leadership style and attitude”. For work-life balance, some sample questions are “I am satisfied with my ability tto meet the needs of my job with those of my personal life” and “I have the time to reach my personal and career goals satisfactorily”.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Demographic Analysis: Table 1 shows the demographic analysis of the responses against Gender, Experience in current organization, Age and Income. It is clear from the table that data is not biased towards gender as 42.3 % of the total response was from Male and 57.7 % of the responses are collected from Male. Maximum of the responses have noted their experience in the current organization from a rage of 6 years to 15 years i.e. 58 % approx. So our data is valid for studying Employee Longevity.Also 73% of the responses have noted their age from 26 years to 45 years. The Income level has also noted to be maximum fro the range of 10 Lakh to 15 Lakh per annum.

Table 1: Demographic Analysis of the Respondents

Sl. No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	93	42.3%
	Female	127	57.7%
	Total	220	100
2	Experience in current Company		
	0-5	72	32.7%
	6-10	81	36.8%
	11-15	48	21.8%
	More than 15	19	8.6%
	Total	220	100
3	Age		
	Below 25 & 25 yrs	21	9.5%
	26-35 yrs	49	22.2%
	36-45 yrs	110	50%
	46-55 yrs	32	14.5%
	Above 55 yrs	8	3.6%
	Total	220	100
4	Income		
	Upto 5,00,000	49	22%
	5,00,001-10,00,000	52	23.5%
	10,00,001-15,00,000	73	33%
	15,00,001-20,00,000	17	7.3%
	Above 20,00,000	29	13.2%
	Total	220	100

5.2 Correlation

Table 2 shows the correlation study of the responses where Pearson correlation is calculated to show the relationship between Recovery related self efficacy and employee longevity. As this study has taken 2 dimensions under The dependent variable, Employee Longevity,i.e. Work life Balance and Job Satisfaction , the correlation of recovery related self efficacy with individual dimensions have also shown. It is clear from the table that Recovery related self efficacy is having positive correlation with Work life balance and job satisfaction and also with Employee Longevity as the significant p value is 0.000 for all three variables. Also With Employee longevity the correlation is recorded to be 0.362 , that is the correlation is falling in the range of +0.25 to +0.50 showing a moderate positive correlation.

Table 2: Correlations

		Recovery related Self efficacy	Work Life Balance	Job Satisfaction	Employee Longevity
Recovery related Self efficacy	Pearson Correlation	1	.302**	.340**	.362**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
Work Life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.302**	1	.697**	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.340**	.697**	1	.697**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
Employee Longevity	Pearson Correlation	.362**	.810**	.697**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

5.3 Regression with Job satisfaction and Work- life Balance :

Table 3 shows the Model Summary of Recovery related self efficacy with Work life balance and also with Job satisfaction. It is clear that both of the models are fit as for both the model , $p=0.000$ and $p<0.01$. Also the R2 value shows that Work life balance is 9.1% affected by Recovery related self efficacy. Also it is clear from Model Summary-II that Recovery related self efficacy has 11.6% magnitude impact on Job satisfaction. This means that recovery related self efficacy is affecting more on Job satisfaction rather than Work life Balance.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Recovery related self Efficacy (RRSE) with Work Life Balance(WLB) and Job Satisfaction (JS) individually

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.302 ^a	.091	.089	.64906

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Life Balance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.340 ^a	.116	.114	.64027

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction

5.4 Regression with Employee Longevity

Table 4 , Table 5 & Table 6 show the regression analysis of recovery related self efficacy with employee longevity (beta = 0.362, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.01$). This is a result of each employee's unique capacity for stress recovery. It is not a given that every employee will need the same or greater degree of psychological disconnection from the company in order to decompress and prepare for future challenges. They take time, depending on how capable or self-sufficient the employee is. Some people may

require more time than necessary, while others may require less time. but in order to mentally recharge for the new objectives, it's critical to take a mental vacation from the workplace. Employees are more productive and willing to stay in the office if they receive the necessary psychological time off from the company. Employee longevity is therefore impacted by this issue. Furthermore, the R2 value is 0.131, indicating that recovery-related self-efficacy is responsible for a 13% magnitude change in employee longevity. Here, it affirms the objective which postulated that the dimension "recovery related self-efficacy" has an impact on employee longevity, and it indicates that this impact is substantial.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.362 ^a	.131	.129	.63474

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Longevity

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.488	1	26.488	65.744	.000 ^b
	Residual	176.066	437	.403		
	Total	202.554	438			

a. Dependent Variable: Recovery related self Efficacy
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Longevity

Table 6: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.851	.183		10.103	.000
	Employee Longevity	.375	.046	.362	8.108	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Recovery related self Efficacy

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research is intended to work on 2 major objectives. First was to identify whether there is any correlation between recovery related self efficacy and employee longevity and the second one was to identify the impact of recovery related self efficacy on employee longevity. Again Employee longevity was studied from 2 approaches , job satisfaction and work life balance. From Table 2 , it is clear that recovery related self efficacy is correlated with employee longevity as the correlation is 0.362, which means, correlation is positive at significant level 0.00 and confidence interval being 99%. Also this table is identifying the correlation of recovery related self efficacy with job satisfaction being 0.340 with p=0.000 and p<0.01.

Also with work life balance , the correlation is 0.302 and p=0.000 , p<0.01. So the results are accepting the alternate hypothesis that recovery related self efficacy is correlated with employee longevity. The interpretation is when employees are getting time to recover themselves from work related stress, then they are able to work with new energy on the next day and this also strengthens their decision of staying back for longer in that organization.

Second to be noted that when employees are getting time to recover their stress and reenergize according to their self efficacy , then they are able to manage their work family life and also they are satisfied with their job. But then if they are not getting the recovery time from organization, or if their self efficacy demand more time to get recovered and they are not getting then it might increase imbalance in family and work which may lead to the decision of quitting from organization. So here one first objective is fulfilled and hypothesis is accepted that Recovery related self efficacy has a positive correlation with employee longevity.

Coming to second hypothesis which says that there is impact of recovery related self efficacy on employee longevity, Author has showcased the analysis through Table 3, Table 4, Table 5 & Table 6. Table 3 depicts the regression relation between recovery related self efficacy with work life balance, which shows that 9% impact of recovery related self efficacy is there on work life balance, one of the two factors under employee longevity. Interpreting the idea that, when employees are able to recover themselves from office work stress, then are able to manage work and family life. Similarly the Model Summary II of Table 3 depicts that 11.6% change in job satisfaction is affected by recovery related self efficacy.

This means that employees are satisfied with their job when they are able to bear the stress and can be able to recover themselves easily from it during non working hours (Cabrera-Aguilar et al., 2023). Table 4,5 & 6 depicts the regression analysis and model summary of recovery related self efficacy with employee longevity. Table 5 shows that 13.1% of employee longevity is explained through recovery related self efficacy with $p=0.00$ (Table 5) and Table 6 shows that the effect of recovery related self efficacy on employee longevity is 36.2%. It accepts our hypothesis that recovery related self efficacy have a impact on employee longevity.

The reason behind this is proven from various other supportive studies that each employee have their own level of self ability to recover from workload related stress. When they are not able to recover or if they are not getting ample amount of time to recover from their stress and then again they have to work for the next day , then this procrastination might lead to separation from the organization.

From this discussion, a conceptual model has been framed in Fig.1 where the beta value is mentioned for identifying the impact of recovery related self efficacy on employee longevity.

Fig 1: Conceptual Model (Source: Author Self Compilation)

7. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

From the above discussion , it is clear that recovery related self efficacy has a moderate impact on employee longevity. When employee's retention is a major issue, organizations should look forward for the concerns which are important for the employees and can affect their decision to continue in an organization.

Employee longevity can benefit both the employees and the employers. For employees it brings stability and work life balance and for the employer it brings organization sustainability. So the factors effecting employee longevity should not be ignored. Recovery from work is a right of employees and it should be given by the organization for enhancing employee well being in a long run.

8. FUTURE SCOPE

Further research can be done on impact of recovery related self efficacy on other factors of employee longevity other than job satisfaction and employee work life balance. Secondly, researchers can also explore different other sectors of India and across the globe to check the implications of recovery related self efficacy.

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